

STUDYING WORKS OF FUTURE ARTISTS FORMATION

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Annotation: In this article, future artists will be able to show changes in our environment through research, be able to clearly see the current situation and know in advance how to achieve the goal, the specificity of the research methodology is necessary for further professional activity.

Key words: study. color, composition, rhythm, tone.

Under the leadership of President Shavkat Miromanovich Mirziyoyev on March 19, 2019 to raise awareness of youth. Involvement of youth in culture, arts and sports, formation of skills in the effective use of information technology, motivation of young people to read books and employment of women. had driven. The first of the five initiatives is to increase the interest of young people in music, fine arts, literature, theater and all kinds of art, to show their talent in practice. On this basis, in order to increase the effectiveness of spiritual work in the system of the Ministry of Higher and Secondary Special Education, as a result of the decision No. PQ-4304 of May 3, 2019 in the regions of the republic and Karakalpak State University named after Berdak directions increased. Currently, students are studying in these areas. In order to become a talented artist, students studying in these areas, first of all, have to work hard, because the goal can be achieved through independent work in this area.

The future artist will get acquainted with painting etudes, starting with rehearsals in the first painting. That is a well-structured still life a quick artistic solution to assignments to depict natural landscapes is commonly referred to as an etude. Such work requires the artist to have extensive experience and knowledge of the environment. thanks for the knowledge

Through the study of the etymology, the artist learns the exact direction. The study of the young artist to perform the etude at a professional level are two important tests for him to create imaginary landscapes:

from the first; the knowledge and skills he has acquired in painting in the process of reading are visible in the autumn, secondly; In the study, the young artist's individual attitude to nature, life and creativity, his ideal professionalism will benefit.

Through the study, he learns to deal with changes in the environment, to see the current situation clearly and to know in advance how to achieve the goal. Thus, by studying the specificity of the colors in nature, he develops the knowledge of the light and shadow in a still life, the correct placement of things. Usually the study is done very quickly and should be done in half an hour to an hour.

In this case, it is necessary to show the harmony and naturalness of colors. When the artist is working on an etude, he finds the location and color of large details with large cysts, does not write small details. The most convenient time to work on the etude is to depict the natural landscape at sunrise and sunset in the morning. The reason is that when the sun rises and falls, it uses a few colors and inspires the artist in a beautiful way. The most comfortable fabrics are cardboard or plywood, which are not too big is coming. The landscape of nature attracts future artists. When working on the first etude, the future artist will not be able to achieve a satisfactory result. His sketches are not very similar to nature, that is, they can not replace the colors. Only through still life, composition, copying, and further practice does the gene begin to overcome the difficulties of etude work.

The future artist follows important rules in the study. First of all, it is necessary to pay attention to the layout. (Figure 1)

Figure 1

If you want to describe the events on the ground, then you need to draw the horizon line up, if you want to describe the events in the sky, then you need to draw the horizon line down. As soon as the artist sees the natural landscape that he likes, and which evokes feelings in him, and which makes him feel deeply, the deep house begins on the composition of the future work: first, the shape and form of the etude are determined.

Figure 2

then it is applied to the compositional construction of the work to be narrated through this form. Etude is an auxiliary material for the depiction of a future natural landscape, which can reach the level of a fully developed independent work. Most

importantly, the etude pays great attention to saturation (tone) and color matching, color matching.

The impressive landscape found in Etyul can fade when light in tone and color, and then burn off its aesthetic beauty. To do this, it is necessary to follow the etude to maintain the harmony of form and color, taking into account the size and composition of the picture-nature. Very few artists create a landscape-painting based on their imagination without first working on the study. However, this method does not always lead to the successful publication of the work. Such canvases lack the cheerfulness of life, the brightness of colors that can be reflected in the study. .It is a difficult task to work on a landscape in nature without working on a study. With the passage of time, the hue and color in nature, the state of light and shadow, change. Therefore, achieving color matching is complicated. In such cases, depending on the harmony of color, the appearance of the scene becomes the main artistic and aesthetic reality.

In addition, the future artist must analyze the artistic works of the body and study their proportions in order to work on the study. For this purpose, it is useful to study the creative work of several well-known artists on the same subject. Of these, I. Levitan, I. Shishkin, N. Karaxan, A.Kuinji, I.Xaydarov, Z.Inogamov, A.Savrasov, U.Tansikbaev, A. The seasonal landscape of artists like Muminov can explore the relationship between the genre's creative work. [R. Khasanov, p. 139] Such works serve to strengthen the knowledge of the future artist in painting. deepen

We are confident that the students trained in these specialties will become the masters of the future, the successors of the well-known artists of the republic, who will contribute to the visual development of our country and become among the foreign artists who have developed in international art exhibitions. The President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Miromanovich Mirziyoyev said in his speech: "Our people must live in harmony with us." Therefore, we will never tire of doing our best to serve the people, to depict the life and social status of our people on wide

canvases with our own words. We hope that our state will dedicate the knowledge of our students to the development of fine arts. Development

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